

* How to access higher dimensions?

You see, for a 3D object to go in a 2D, it must lose one of its axes (z axis). It will be left with only x and y axis, hence sending a 3d object in 2d, making it lose all of its 3d characteristics. For a 2D object to go in the 1D space, it must lose its axes (can be either x or y). So, if an object must advance from lower dimension to higher dimension, it must gain a new axis, and that's the basic geometry. What I want is to imagine yourself as a viewer of a 4D plane, looking at an object, moving from 0th dimension to the 3rd Dimension. Notice something? Every time that object gains a new axis, new features get added to it. Like when it came into the first dimension, it gained 1 axis, it gained something new, leaving the 0th dimension object (a dot) alone in the lower dimension and that line travels to the 1st dimension. Where is that dot now? It's a part of the 1st dimension line. Look at that line and one single point carefully, think from the dot's perspective, it has more dots in front of itself, and keep that in mind, MORE IN FRONT, since this keyword is important. Now, add another axis. Now that plane simple line has one more axis to explore, hence that simple line, with 3 more lines, connect each other and form a shape for the first time. Now, go back in the prospect of a dot. Now, there isn't a dot in front of you, that dot is in side of you now, and below you are another dot, MORE DOTS AROUND YOU. NOTE that till now, more dots have joined the axis, but none of them are residing inside the initial dot, they are all near the dot. Now, let's add another axis, the z axis, and now the playground is 3D, giving another possibility for shapes to form. More shapes come together and form new shapes. Go back to your initial dot and see more dots and in either in front of you, or behind you or you the dots are both in front and behind, thus keeping you at center. NOTE that till now we have added 3 axis and none of them added a new dot inside the initial dot, thus not breaking the pattern of nature to add more in front/back/front/behind. So, if we now add one more axis then the new axis will come in new axis, but that axis won't add another dot inside any other dot. So, now let's add the 4th axis, the w-axis. Position of the axis has been shown below for better understanding.

* 4th Dimensional axis image and gif*

Imagining the fourth axis in the 3d sphere won't make sense, since what we imagine will always lies within the boundaries of the 3rd dimension. So, imagine 4th dimension as a dimension of energy spheres or the realm of ghost, where the beings can access anything and everything in 3rd and lower dimensions. It is said that being of 4th dimension can be seen inside the human body and outside at the same time. So, the brings of 4th dimension, they can pass through human body, see inside it and outside at the same time. The 4th dimension is got INSIDE the 3rd

but is like a energy ball (or actual aura which is emitted when Saiyan's powerup), covering the 3rd dimensional objects. If we were to slice a 3d object perfectly, we get to see a 2d shape. So, if object of 4d is to be cut perfectly, then a 3d object is to be formed.

* Dimensional edging

When a phenomenon that is happening in the higher dimension affects lower dimension too, then that incident is called DIMENSIONAL EDGING. A perfect example of this in 3d dimension is "Space" and "Gravity". Certain calculations when done on blackholes/white holes or anything else that is outside our planet has a great possibility to be an outcome of something that's happening in 4D, since the 3d realm is not bound to be affected only by 3d but higher dimension too. As for things happening on Earth, the gravitational force of earth is responsible for that. Not just earth, but anything happening on a planet can almost be defined using its gravitational force, but that gravitational force might be getting in influenced by something of 4d, which cannot be seen or sensed by our 3d knowledge.

* Dimensional transversion

Let's say you want to access 2d while being a 3d human, how can you? As discussed above, you must remove one of the axes (z) axis from your body, meaning, you must compress yourself to become as thin as paper, then only you will be able to access the 2nd dimension. What if a living creature from 4d wants to visit 3d? What are they going to do? Exactly what has been done by you when you wanted to visit 2d, remove one axis. You had to remove Z axis from your body, and they must remove W axis from their body. It's like cutting yourself from front and back to access 2d but cutting yourself from diagonal to diagonal (another term will be used in later research papers to explain this diagonal-to-diagonal cutting) to access 3d. Thus, removing one axis from the initial axis is called DIMENSIONAL TRANSVERSION.

* Dimensional rift

It's not always necessary that one universe of any dimension stays in that dimension, having more axis and harder geometry can also cause instability in that universe. In such case, the universe fails to handle its dimensional properties and shifts to a lower dimension. This phenomenon is called DIMENSIONAL RIFT. It is not bound to happen to a whole universe, but can also happen to a single atom, thus rifting that particular atom from higher dimension to lower dimension. This might have happened in our 3d universe, but we either didn't notice it, or haven't encountered such incident till now.